

POVERTY, UNEMPLOYMENT AND YOUTH INVOLVEMENT IN CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA

Gbenemene Kpae and Aaron Ayanabia

Department of Sociology, University of Port Harcourt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14961235>

Abstract: The extent of youth involvement in internet crime in Nigeria cannot be underestimated. Daily, the number of youths involved in cybercrime keeps increasing. This is due to the harsh economic environment in which our young people had to survive coupled with high level of unemployment that has gone into double digits. The high level of joblessness in Nigeria has left many youths impoverished. Many have resorted to a life of crime as a way of acquiring the material things that is highly cherished in Nigeria, and as well as getting back at society which has failed to give them an opportunity for a better life. This paper examines the extent to which poverty and unemployment have caused Nigerian youth to be involved in all forms of criminality, especially cybercrime. The paper is rooted in Cohen and Felson (1979) routine activity theory. It recommends the establishment of ICTC centers in all police departments and greater coordination between the police and the FFCC in the investigation and prosecution of cybercriminals.

Keywords: Youth involvement, Cybercrime, Unemployment, Poverty, Routine activity theory

INTRODUCTION

Nigerian youth involvement in internet crime is not a new phenomenon. In fact, since the early 1990s, Nigerians have been noted for being involved in cybercrime, however, it was not as widespread as it is today. At its earlier stage, it was limited to Advance Fee Fraud or "419", where some Nigerian crooks try to obtain money fraudulently from some foreign nationals, mostly Americans, on the promise of an oil contract. These fraudsters claimed through e-mails that they owned oil wells and were looking for would-be-investors. Many desperate foreigners seeking for quick means of making money from Africa became victims of these criminals.

The growth of internet communications also means the proliferation of cybercrime such as identity theft, extortion, advance fee fraud, digital piracy, online viewing of pornography, theft of data, cyber trespassing, etc. Cybercrime include Malware, Spyware, Viruses, Phishing, and e-Scams. While the cybercrimes that attack the computer directly include denial-of-service attacks, (DoS attack) or distributed denial-of-service attack (DoS attack). In addition, the advent of social media such as Face Book, and twitter has made communication and sharing of pictures of the internet much easier than ever imagined.

The introduction of social media has also brought a new dimension in cybercrime, especially with crimes such as stalking and murder beginning to rare their ugly heads. Majority of the people involved in these crimes are young unemployed men from poor hornet who spend their idle time searching for victims on the net. "The harsh economic climate has forced many youths in Nigeria to the life of crime as a way of survival. There is no serious effort on the part of the government to create jobs as a way of reducing the number of youths lured into engaging in cybercrime. The situation is made worse in a society such as Nigeria that culturally abhors poverty but glorifies

materialism, and less emphasis on hard work. Most young people just want to be seen as being successful. Unemployment in Nigeria is pervasive, and there is no sign that the government is doing something tangible to create jobs for its teeming youth. When people are unemployed for a prolonged period of time, they are not only poor, but suffer from frustration, and may be forced into a life-of crime. 'Since cybercrime came to public attention, the government's efforts have not been on tackling the root causes of youth involvement in cybercrime (poverty and unemployment), but to deal with the crime itself, which it believes has damaged the image of Nigeria both home and abroad. Since law enforcement agencies are ill equipped and lack the training to investigate internet crimes, the government reaction has been the establishment of two key agencies: the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC) and the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), with responsibilities to tackle the menace of internet crime. The two institutions have done tremendous work in curbing the menace of cybercrime, but the EFCC has been particularly noted for arresting and prosecuting internet offenders. Since its establishment about 13 years ago, the EFCC has been able to restore international confidence in Nigeria and its ability to fight cybercrime. However, despite, its efforts, poor funding and limited resources makes it difficult for the agency to investigate and prosecute the growing cases of cybercrime in Nigeria. The impact of cybercrime on Nigeria has been tremendous. Apart from destroying the reputation of Nigeria abroad, its economic impact has been more damaging since the emergence of the phenomenon. According to Kilian Strauss of the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE), the damage caused by cybercrime is estimated at \$100 billion dollars annually. Apart from the financial losses suffered as a result of cybercrime, other effects of cybercrime include diminished consumer confidence, and lost productivity.

CONCEPTUAL CLERIFICATION

Cybercrime: It refers to crimes that are committed with the aid of the internet. It involves the use of computers and the internet to commit crimes such as fraud, e-mail scams, hacking, piracy, and distribution of hostile software (virus) denial of service attacks, theft of data, extortion, stacking, and murder.

Involvement: It refers to participation in an illegal activity with the sole aim of getting **gratification** or some **financial, reward**.

Unemployment: It refers to a person who is willing to a given wage rate, but could not find job. It also refers to a state of being unemployed.

Poverty: A person is poor if he cannot afford the basic necessities of life such as food, cloth and a good shelter.

Youth: It refers to a person between the ages of 15 and 34 years. It constitutes the most energetic and vibrant segment of most country's population. According to the UN records, youths outnumber the other segments of the population.

REVIEW OF LITERATURES

The relationship between poverty and crime, especially cybercrime cannot be over-emphasized. When an individual is unemployed for a much-extended period of time, it creates a feeling of hopelessness in the person, which in many cases, propels the individual into criminal activity. Many unemployed persons are poor and poverty breeds crime. Odumosu (1999: 73) argues that poverty as a social condition or existence plays a vital role in crime. Odumosu also notes that:

The poor are led to crime because of their relative deprivation and acute sense of want... this observation seems

to tally largely with the existing reality in Nigeria today where a person's worth in life and his contribution to society is measured by his wealth.

The effect of poverty on crime can be explained through a variety of reasons. First, there is a higher rate of mental illness in the poor than the rich. Second, poverty can lead to high levels of stress that in turn may lead individuals to commit crime, especially cybercrime. Lastly, poverty may lead to an actual or perceived inferior education, low self-esteem, which could cause youths to engage in internet crime as well as other social vices. Further, crime offers a way in which impoverished people can obtain material goods that they cannot obtain 'through legitimate means. For many people, the prize that crime yields may outweigh the risk of being caught, especially given that their opportunity cost is lower than that of a wealthier person.

Unemployment as a concept has been defined by various scholars; Gbosi (1990: 117), for instance, asserts that there is no precise definition of unemployment. However, he sees unemployment as a situation in which people are willing to work on a prevailing wage rate but cannot find jobs. He places emphasis on willingness and asserts that anybody who is not seeking paid employment should not be counted as part of the labour force. Diejomoah et al (1971: 129) believe' that one of the consequences of generalized chronic unemployment is the rising wave of crime in almost all parts of Nigeria. However, Clinard and Abbott, (1973: 180) dispute this finding. They stated that although unemployment is a prominent rationalization given by offenders for indulging in theft, it may not actually be responsible for the culprit's decision to steal. While the? Argument by Olinard and Abbott may seem plausible that not all unemployed people go into criminality, it is indisputable that an idle young person in society such as Nigeria, with no welfare package for the unemployed, may be tempted to join criminal gang if there is pressure from peers or criminal family members.

Origin of the Internet

The history of the internet began with the development of electronic computers; in the 1950's. This began with point-to-point computers between mainframe computers, and terminals, expanded to point-to-point connections between computers and packet switched networks such as ARPANET, MARK 1 TYMNET in the UK. CYCLADES, MERIT NETWORK, TYMNET AND TELENET were developed in the late 1960's and early 1970, using variety of protocols. The ARPANET, in particular, led to the development of protocols for internet working, where multiple separate networks could be joined together into a network of networks.

In 1982, the Internet Protocol Suite (TCPLIPS) was standardized and the concept - of World-Wide Network of interconnected TCP/IP networks called the INTERNAL was introduced. Access to the ARPANET was expanded in 1981 when the National Science Foundation (NSF) developed the Computer Science Network (CSNET) and in 1986 where NSENET provided access to super computer sites in the United States from research and education organizations. Commercial Internet Service Providers (ISP's) began to emerge in the late 1980's and 1990's. The ARPANET was decommissioned in 1990. The internet was commercialized in 1995 when NSFNET was decommissioned removing the las- restrictions on the use of the internet to carry commercial traffic.

Since the mid 1990's, the internet has had drastic impact on culture anc commerce in Nigeria including the rise of near instant communication by electronic mail, instant messaging, Voice Over Internet Protocol (VOIP) "phone calls", two way-- interactive video calls and World Wide Web with its discussion forums, blogs, social networking

and online shopping sites. The research and education community continues to develop and use advanced networks such as NSF's very high-speed Backbone Network Service) (VBNS), Internet 2 and National Lambda Rail. Increasing amounts of data are transmitted at higher and higher speeds over fiber optic networks operating at: 1-Gbit/s, 10-Gbit/s, or more. The internet continues to grow, driven by ever greater amounts of online information and knowledge, commerce, entertainment and social networking.

History of Cybercrime

The Nigerian 419 scam is a form of advanced fraud similar to the Spanish Prisoner scam dating back to the late 19th century. During this period, businesses were contacted by an individual allegedly trying to smuggle someone connected to a wealthy family out of prison in Spain. In exchange for assistance, the scammer promised to share money with the victim in exchange for a small amount of money to bribe prison guards.

One variant of the scam may date back to the 18th and 19th centuries, as a very similar letter, titled, "The Letter from Jerusalem" is seen in the memoirs of Eugene Francois Vdocq, a former French criminal and private investigator. Another variant of the scam dating back to 1830, is very similar to what is passed via email today (Wikipedia, 2013).

Edet (2012) believes that cybercrime may have emerged in conjunction with the building of the first computer networks, however it was not as sophisticated as it is today. This is because, in the early days of computing, the average criminal did not have either the necessary hardware or the technical expertise to use the computer as a tool to commit crimes.

Computers were million-dollar mainframe monstrosities, and only a few of them were in existence. Cybercrime emerged and grew as computing became easier and less expensive, and when criminals recognized that computers store something of value, particularly information. But since the data was stored on a closed, standalone system, it was difficult for people to steal. However, when that data began to move from one computer to another over networks, especially with the commercialization of computers, it increased cybercrimes. This is because numerous people and businesses were using the same computer, the data and programs stored on it became vulnerable. Edet (2012) contends that since commercialization of computers opened the first doors to hacking, all efforts of system administrators, security product vendors, and law enforcement to tackle cybercrime have yielded little result.

While the timeline for the emergence of the different forms of cybercrime may be debatable, records show that major incidents of cybercrime began to emerge in the late 1960s. The word "hacker", for instance, originally referred to someone who was considered a "real programmer" who had mastered the computer systems of the day and was able to manipulate programs to do more than they were originally intended to do. In the late 1960s and early 1970s, hackers became an underground radical movement against established authorities (Edet, 2012).

Classification of Cybercrime

The Council of Europe's Convention on Cybercrime defines three types of computer crimes namely:

1. Offences that are computer related or facilitated;
2. Offences that are content related;
3. Offences related to infringements of copyright and related rights.

However, Dr. Pavan Duggal of Cybernet.net believes cybercrime should be categorized as crime against person,

against property, and against the government. Cybercrime can also be categorized into two types namely: (1) crimes that target computers directly, (2) the ones facilitated by computer networks or devices. Crimes that target computer networks or devices includes computer viruses, denial of service attacks, and Malware (Malicious codes), while crimes that use computer networks or device for other purposes includes cyber stalking, fraud and identity theft, hacking and cyber trespassing

Cybercrime in Nigeria

The modern 419 scam in Nigeria became popular in the 1980s during the hyper-corrupt "Second Republic" government of President Shehu Shagari. There are many variants of the letter sent. One of these letters via postal mail was sent to a woman's husband about what do with profits from some business investment. Other official looking letters were sent from a writer claiming to be a director of the state-owned Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation. Yet, other variants have involved mention of a Nigerian Prince or member of late General Sani Abacha's family seeking to transfer large sums of money out of the country (Wikipedia, 2013), One reason why Nigeria may have been singled out, according to Wikipedia, is "because of the comical, almost ludicrous nature of the promise of West African riches from a Nigerian Prince." It, however, contends that while Nigeria is most often the nation referred to in these scams, they may be originated in other nations as well. For instance, in 2006, 61% of Internet criminals were traced to locations in the United States, while 16% were traced to the United Kingdom and 6% to locations in Nigeria. Other nations known to have high incidence of advance fee fraud include Cote d'Ivoire, Togo, South Africa, the Nether lands, and Spain.

Theoretical Framework

The Nigerian youth involvement in cybercrime can be situated in the Routine Activity Theory by Cohen and Felson (1979). The basic premise of the theory is that in order for crime to occur, victims and motivated offenders must converge in space and time where there is the absence of a suitable guardian. Thus, much of the research on opportunity theory examines how routine daily activities of individuals influence the likelihood that they will be exposed to high-risk situations and environments that places them in closer proximity to motivated offenders (Altheimer, 2008: 14). Cohen and Felson, (1979: 593) defines routine daily activities as "any recurrent: and prevalent activities which provide for basic population and individual's needs." Therefore, individuals whose recurrent and prevalent activities place them in closer proximity to motivated offenders are exposed to high risk of victimization.

According to opportunity theory, lifestyles are shaped by "individuals" collective, responses or adaptations to various role expectations and structural constraints (Meie and Meithe, 1993: 466). Role expectations and cultural restraints play a critical role in this process because they express shared societal expectations about appropriate behavior for individuals with certain attributes. Adherence to societal expectations leads to the establishment of routine daily activities for those individuals, thereby, influence in their risk for victimization. Many jobless youths in Nigeria are motivated offenders who converge in time and space with innocent victims that they prey upon. The victim can either be a Nigerian or other foreign national, provided they are on the web at that time of communication. The daily activity of the. Victim, which is to browse the web regularly puts him/her in close proximity with motivated offenders and the likelihood that he/she may be victimize. Moreover, the advent of cell phones in Nigeria has made cybercrime very difficult to police. The presence of a suitable guardian; which in this

case is the police or other security agents, cannot deter motivated offenders, because the victim is not in physical contact with the offender, but his daily activities put him in close proximity with the motivated offender and makes his victimization much more likely to occur.

Conclusion

This paper examines the extent to which poverty and unemployment have driven Nigerian youths to engage in cybercrime. Many people in Nigeria are poor, especially, the young ones from poor homes. As many youths cannot find gainful employment, so they find illegitimate means to achieve financial prosperity. Since the early 1990s, Nigerians have been noted for their involvement in internet crime through sending, fictitious mails to foreigners to come and invest in Nigerian oil industry. Many innocent foreigners, mostly Americans, have been defrauded millions of dollars due to such fraudulent mails. The government reactions have been swift, rather than addressing the root causes of the problem, it has rather tried to deal with the crime itself that has destroyed the image of Nigeria abroad. The IC, PC and EFCC were established to investigate and prosecute offenders. The EFCC has achieved tremendous success in this direction, but is limited by poor funding.

Internet crime in Nigeria is situated in the routine activity theory of Cohen and Felson, who notes that crime can only take place when there is convergence in time and space of a victim and motivated offenders, and the absence of a suitable guardian. When an individual spends a lot of time on the web, he puts himself/herself at great risk of being victimized. The introduction of social networks such as Facebook and Twitter have led to increase in crimes such as stalking and harassment, extortion, and murder. The advent of cellular phones in Nigeria has also made it difficult for security agents to police cybercrime because young men simply use their phones at home to communicate and chat with anybody in the world.

Unlike most conventional crimes, cybercrime is without a physical victim since there is no physical contact between the victim and motivated offender, however, its impact on society is tremendous. As the world becomes a global village through internet communication, so, there is increase in cybercrime. This unconventional crime is very difficult for police to monitor and prosecute offenders because they are carried out in people's homes. The government should properly fund the EFCC so that it could investigate and prosecute cyber criminals. It should also establish a special IUC unit in all police departments with sole responsibility to track down people who engage in internet crime. Police officers and other security agents should be trained in the investigation and prosecution of cybercriminals. Finally, there should be synergy between the police and EFCC in the investigation and prosecution of internet criminals.

References

- Alzheimer, I. (2008). *Do Guns Mutter? A Multi-level Cross Notional Examination of, Gun Availability on Assault and Robbery Victimization*. *Western Criminology* 9, 9:32.
- Cohen, L. E. and M. Felson (1979). *Social Change and Crime rate trends. A Routine Approach*. *American Sociological Review* 44: 558-608.
- Uiejomoah et al, (1971). *Unemployment in Nigeria, an 'Economic Analysis of \Scope, trends and Policy issues*. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies* Vol. 13, No. 2, July 1971
- Gbosi, A. (2005). *Fundamentals of Modern Economic Analysis*. Sodek; Associates: Port' Harcourt. in *Crime and Justice*, Vol. 17, edited by M. Tonry. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Odumosu, L. (2000). *Social Costs of Poverty: The Case of Crime in Nigeria*. *Journal of Social Development*. Vol. 14, No. 2, 71-85.